

THE MIGRATION PATTERNS AND HUMAN SECURITY IN AFRICA WITH REFERENCE TO THE AFRICAN AGENDA 2063

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates migration patterns and human security in Africa, with reference to the aspiration of the African Agenda 2063. It highlights that Africa is often seen as a continent of mass migration due to conflict and poverty in countries such as Sudan, Cameroon, Democratic Republic of Congo, and Nigeria, among others, has migration deeply embedded in its history. The paper emphasizes that despite migration being a key aspect of development and internationalisation, it remains a contentious issue in policy and practice across Africa. Immigrants are often blamed for major issues like crime, competition for job opportunities, and resource strain, leading to the tension between the local inhabitants and immigrants. The political situations in Zimbabwe, Nigeria, Sudan, Cameroon, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, and Mozambique, in most cases, coupled with the dominance of rebel groups, have threatened human security in these countries. Consequently, the decline in human security and the high poverty rates have influenced an unprecedented level of migration in Africa. The paper, adopting a qualitative research method based on a desktop study, finds a link between socioeconomic development and the geographical location of African emigration. It confirms migration theories, stating that poorer residents of African countries have limited abilities to improve their living standards, and their movements are often confined within Africa. The paper concludes that Africa continues to face increased migration and growing antimigrant sentiments, leading to policies favouring deterrence over inclusivity. It underscores the need for improved and harmonised migration management policies as a critical priority for African governments.

Keywords: Development, Human Security, Migrants, Migration, Poverty.

INTRODUCTION

Africa is often perceived as a continent of mass migration driven by violent conflict, human insecurity, and poverty (Flahaux and De Haas, 2016). Migration is considered a significant aspect of Africa's history, which can be traced back to the nomadic lifestyle. Many African countries, such as South Africa, Zimbabwe, Nigeria and Ghana, have been shaped by migration, whether it involves internal migration from rural to urban areas (Flahaux and De Haas, 2016). The current conflicts in Sudan, Cameroon, and DRC, and the political instability in Zimbabwe and Mozambique which threatens human security in these countries, have influenced the migration process. Therefore, individuals have ventured to South Africa as indentured labourers in search of employment and other forms of human security. Despite this, migration remains a contentious issue in both policy and practice across Africa (Mlambo, Thusi, and Ndlovu, 2022). This is evident in how most South African citizens perceive and interact with migrants. The current discourse on migration often portrays immigrants as responsible for major social issues such as crime, higher competition for job opportunities, and resource strain, leading to increased poverty (Check, 2022). Consequently, human insecurity in various countries has resulted in many undocumented immigrants and asylum seekers. The purpose of this paper is to examine migration patterns and human security in Africa with reference to the African Agenda 2063.

The research carried out by Check (2022) indicates that most Africans carry proper passports, visas, and other necessary travel documents when traveling. Flahaux and De Haas (2016) challenge the idea that African migration is distinctive and fundamentally separate from migration in other regions. The Gaza and Israel conflicts, as well as the Ukraine and Russia conflicts, have led to increased migration, the presence of refugee camps, and more asylum seekers due to threats to human security. More proof suggests that numerous Africans move due to factors such as family, employment, or education, mirroring patterns seen in different regions. Research in the Great Lakes area suggested that although conflict is a major factor in forced migration, it is also essential to account for continuous social factors that influence movement, such as seeking education, connections, or an improved lifestyle in cities (Adeleke and Olawale, 2023). Official statistics show that there were 2.4 million immigrants and those living in refugee-like conditions, which represents 14% of the total number of refugees in Africa (Sparks, 2016). Although higher than in other areas, this shows that around 86% of migration within Africa is not mainly related to conflict (Sparks, 2016). Although there is a growing amount of detailed data on African migration, access to the data is still restricted and mostly centers on migration to Europe from a handful of extensively studied African nations such as Morocco, Senegal, Ghana, and South Africa (Mlambo, Thusi, and Ndlovu, 2022). Comprehensive data on migration patterns within, to and from Africa in recent decades have been missing (Check, 2022). This is essential not only to obtain a more profound understanding of African migration trends and confirm widespread beliefs about the significant and growing African migration, but also to add to academic discussions on migration influences.

Check (2022) has challenged traditional push-pull models by arguing that in impoverished societies, development increases rather than decreases migration levels. Additionally, conventional explanations of African migration often overlook the role of African conditions in shaping migration, reflecting a broader Eurocentric focus on migration research. With these

considerations in mind, this article aims to explore migration patterns and human security in Africa in the context of the African Agenda 2063.

Intercontinental migration is emphasized a lot in the scholarly debate, especially movement towards North America or Europe. However, the patterns of intra-African migration and their consequences for human security receive little attention. This oversight restricts the comprehension of how socioeconomic factors and regional policy affect migration patterns within the continent. Despite the Migration Policy Framework Action (MPFA) of the African Union (AU) for Africa, which seeks to provide solace and assistance to internal and external migrants, most African people continue to remain in distress. This is due to political instabilities, poor living standards in their native countries, wars and conflicts, and natural disasters, *inter alia*.

LITERATURE REVIEW

THEORIES GUIDING MIGRATION PATTERNS AND HUMAN SECURITY

Flahaux and De Haas (2016) highlight that Africa is sometimes referred to as a continent of mass displacement due to factors such as poverty, violence, and political instability. The author also notes that migration trends are influenced by media portrayals of boat migrations and large refugee movements. This paper is grounded in migration theory, which encompasses Micro-, Meso-, and Macro theories. Vella (2013) suggests that migration theory incorporates sociology, economics, and geography to understand migration dynamics. The following are some of the key migration theories.

Table 1. Theories Guiding The Study

<i>Micro-level</i>	<i>Meso-level</i>	<i>Macro-level</i>
<i>Migration cause:</i> Individual values/ desires/ expectancies e.g. improving survival, wealth etc.	<i>Migration cause/ perpetuation:</i> Collectives/ social networks e.g. social ties	<i>Migration cause/ perpetuation:</i> Macro-level opportunity structure e.g. economic structure (income and employment opportunities differentials)
<i>Main theories:</i> - Lee's push/ pull factors - Neoclassical micro-migration theory - Behavioural models - Theory of social systems	<i>Main theories:</i> - Social capital theory - Institutional theory - Network theory - Cumulative causation - New Economics of Labour Migration	<i>Main theories:</i> - Neoclassical macro-migration theory - Migration as a system - Dual labour market theory - World systems theory - Mobility Transition

Source: (HagenZanker, 2008; Wickramasinghe & Wimalaratana, 2016).

NEO-CLASSICAL ECONOMICS: MICRO-THEORY OF MIGRATION

According to this concept, rational individuals decide to migrate when they calculate the costs and benefits and believe that moving will result in a positive net return, typically in the form of money (Massey, Arango, Hugo, Kouaouci, Pellegrino & Taylor, 1993). Proponents of this theory contend that international migration is caused by differences in wages and employment rates (Abreu, 2012; O'Reilly, 2022; Hagen-Zanker, 2008). Therefore, migrants expect higher wages and better economic conditions than those in their native countries (Abreu, 2012; Vella, 2013; O'Reilly, 2022; European University Institute, n.d.). To further support this theory, many African countries such as Zimbabwe, South Sudan, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, Namibia, and Mali still face economic challenges, which leads people to migrate to neighboring countries with better economic prospects, including higher wages and more employment opportunities. This theory can be associated with forced and voluntary migration, which also involves pull and push factors (Vella, 2013). While migration may be rationalized, it is not without challenges, as individuals may face difficulties finding employment or settling in the new country upon arrival. This theory suggests that rural individuals are attracted by better employment opportunities in urban areas and are thus drawn to migrate (Hagen-Zanker, 2008).

MESO THEORY OF MIGRATION

Meso methods establish strong connections between macro and microlevel studies, creating a meso link. The meso-level analysis focuses on the interactions between individuals, emphasizing the social activities that enable them and the resources, such as social capital, that individuals can leverage to achieve their goals (Faist, 2000). Meso theories provide significant explanations for the continuation of voluntary migration and the reasons why it originates from specific places. They can also help explain the choice of destination in cases of forced or voluntary migration (United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees, 2002). This theory emphasizes social bonds and network theory to explain the rationale of migration, where individuals may migrate due to international marriages and extended families. According to network theory, migrant networks are webs of kinship, friendship, and shared origins that connect migrants, nonmigrants, and former migrants (King, 2012). Families, prospective migrants, and recently arrived migrants can receive crucial support from these networks as they adapt to their new environment (Garip and Asad, 2015). In the context of Africa's diversity and interconnectedness, Meso theories play a significant role in explaining migration patterns, as individuals can easily establish friendships and relationships that strengthen their social ties. Social bonds and network theory could potentially enhance unity, as emphasized in the African Agenda 2063.

MACRO THEORY OF MIGRATION

Proponents of this theory argue that the demand for labour in developed or resource-rich countries drives international migration. They suggest that there are "pull factors" in developed, affluent nations, such as specific job requirements, which may not be met by the native residents of that country (Wadood, 2023). The theory posits that individuals are not migrating solely based on their reasons but are being drawn from their less technologically advanced and industrialized native countries to developed countries with abundant resources through the dual labour market theory (Ponce, 2016; Wadood, 2023).

THEORY OF FORCED MIGRATION

Smelser and Baltes (2001) understood this theory as inevitably related to change, which is often disruptive and causes displacements. Kobayashi (2019) corroborates the author by indicating that forced migration is empirically observable because it arises from conflicts and natural disasters. Furthermore, forced migration is also related to global change in the political landscape (Vella, 2013). Therefore, changes in politics may lead to political instabilities and conflicts in different countries. Perhaps, the reasons for involuntary migration could include fear of civil war, widespread violence, or official persecution (Vella, 2013).

FACTORS INFLUENCING MIGRATION PATTERNS

For a considerable period, Africa has had a history of being nomadic, which can be traced back to the time of hunter-gatherers. Migration primarily stems from major events and life conditions (Weldemariam, Ayanlade, Borderon & Molsinger, 2023). Migration discussions have predominantly focused on conflict and violence in the Horn of Africa; inadequate governance in the Democratic Republic of the Congo and Somalia; political instability in Burkina Faso; and socioeconomic inequalities and limited economic prospects in nations such as Zimbabwe and Malawi. Furthermore, the unrest in Cameroon and the Democratic Republic of Congo serves as a clear example of human security issues. Climate change-related challenges such as drought, floods, and famine in the Horn of Africa worsen war and violence (Weldemariam et al., 2023). One perspective believes that the reasons for migration are often unrelated to the act of migrating, despite varying viewpoints on the subject. Therefore, it is becoming more crucial to move away from traditional and neo-traditional migration methods that focus on push and pull factors (Check, 2022). New findings suggest that African/EU migration is also driven by improved economic prospects and Africans' desire for a more prosperous life. This implies that the reasons for migrating have a humanitarian element. Economic and social progress in poor countries tends to lead to more migration rather than less (Weldemariam et al., 2023).

Migration has consistently been viewed as a crucial factor in population shifts at different levels, such as local, regional, national, and global (Aborisade and Adebayo, 2018). Various factors play a role in people deciding to move from one area to another. Political instability, civil conflict, forced migration, limited job prospects, a desire for stability in a new nation, and improved pay rates or opportunities are driving factors (Weldemariam et al., 2023). Mueller, Sheriff, Dou, and Gray (2020) suggest that migration is not caused by one factor but by a combination of social,

demographic, economic, climatic, and biological factors. Migration can also be driven by lack of marriage, job offers, unique skills, changes in employment, loss of farms, low wages, retirement, military service, health care, political, ethnic or religious persecution, natural disasters, attacks by outsiders, inheritance, community disruption, desire to travel, social rejection, and forced displacement. Cost of relocation; the existence of family or friends; visual appeal of the neighborhood; natural surroundings; amenities; demographics; unique job opportunities; additional support; financial aid; knowledge; standing; absence of other options. Factors such as significant investments in capital, economic downturns, technological advancements, changes in economic structures, social welfare initiatives, and migration promotion services can influence migration patterns. In some African countries, people are prompted to migrate due to the absence of human security, along with various socioeconomic factors. The Africa Agenda 2063 and the SDGs are still a long way from being achieved due to ongoing conflicts in Sudan, Somalia, Cameroon, Burkina Faso, and Nigeria. The presence of different armed factions in certain African nations such as Nigeria, Cameroon, Mozambique, and the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) still negatively impacts human safety and restricts freedom of movement.

TRENDS IN MIGRATION PATTERNS AND HUMAN SECURITY: AFRICAN PERSPECTIVE

Conflicts, wars, famines, political instability, and natural disasters have increased the trends of migration in Africa (Adeola, 2017). Due to conflicts in Sudan, many Sudanese and refugees are migrating to neighboring countries. Therefore, the High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) (2023) reports that Egypt has already received 255,237 new arrivals, including 68,548 (South Sudan), 60,000 (Chad), 9,730 (Central African Republic), and 3,769 (Ethiopia). Adeola (2017) indicates that by 2015, Africa had more than 12 million displaced people. The trends demonstrated here simply indicate that if the governments and the African Union (AU) do not address the tragedies leading to migration, then the aspirations of Agenda 2063 will remain a pipe dream.

Migration in Africa continues to be the focus. At the current moment, given the conflicts and unrest in DRC due to certain rebels such as the M23, climate change, economic situations (e.g., Zimbabwe), repressive government (e.g., Uganda) and increasing youth populations, the influx of people into different countries will continue to be the discourse in different African countries. The fluctuation of migration from the figure above simply means that the guns of poverty, inequality, unemployment, conflicts, poor economic growth, and famine are not yet silenced to ensure peace, safety, security, and the improvement of living standards in various countries as set out in Africa agenda 2063. Because the conflict in Sudan between military factions in 2023 has resulted in 6 million cross-border displacements (Williams, 2024). Therefore, the trend of migration within and from Africa is expected to increase given the various factors mentioned above. The Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre (IDMC) (2023) shows that conflicts and violence are also major contributors to migration in African countries. In that, IDMC (2023) finds that 1 million people were displaced in 2022 in Mozambique due to conflicts and violence.

Climate change, as observed by Williams (2024), is a major contributor to population displacement in Africa. Williams (2024) projects that due to climate change, Southern Africa will likely experience approximately 800,000 movement of people because of severe flooding, storms, and draught, amongst others. Meanwhile, the Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA) (2024) shows that 1.85 million children in sub-Saharan Africa were left displaced due to natural disasters at the end of 2022. Ndiweni and Musarurwa (2014) refer to the Zimbabwean case regarding the occurrence of natural disasters that lead to internal displacement. Ndiweni and Musarurwa (2014) indicate that Zimbabwe (South) is home to droughts, tropical cyclones, heatwaves, and floods, leading to the reduction of food production, food security, famine and poverty. These factors combined lead to internal displacement and movement of people from one place to the other or even outside their home countries in an attempt to seek rescue. The illustration below seeks to demonstrate internal displacement in Malawi for different reasons.

According to the Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre (IDMC) (2023), the number of people displaced due to storms by 2022 stood at 438 000, flooding at 529 000, earthquakes at 21 000 and wet mass movement which only occurred in 2019 constituted 8,000 people displaced. Furthermore, IDMC (2023) reports that in 2022, 987000 people were internally displaced in Malawi due to disasters. However, this empirical evidence supports the literature on the factors that influence migration patterns. To a greater extent, these factors can also lead people to migrate to various neighboring African countries.

It is clear that a major contributing factor to internal displacement is conflict. Alozieuwa (2014) indicates that Africa has recently witnessed the rise of rebellious and military groups. Hence, Alozieuwa (2014) further shows that Mau-Mau in Kenya is one of the main occurrences of notorious militia groups in Africa. Conflicts are caused by rebels such as M23 in the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), Boko Haram in Nigeria, and Ungiki in Kenya. Lewis (2023) argues that rebellious groups normally cause tragedy in rural areas where the government does not have sufficient information in rural areas. Terrorist attacks in Mozambique in Cabo Delgado province in 2017 were perpetrated by rebellious and armed militias (Neethling, 2021). Meanwhile, Sithole (2022) indicates that the insurgency resulted in the displacement of people in Mozambique. Ntaka (2023: 21) understands that the insurgency occurs due to government failure. This point is further lengthened by Raleigh (2016: 283), who shows that political and militia violence is attributed to failing and predatory states, which leads to civil wars.

Unfortunately, conflicts and wars occur under the tutelage of the African Union (AU) and circumvent the aspirations of the African Agenda (2063). It is highly likely that if conflicts are not addressed, then aspiration 4 (A Peaceful and Secure Africa) and goal 14 (A Stable and Peaceful Africa) will remain a mere gesture remote from practical reality. Niyitunga and Wamaitha (2023: 27) ask this question: Why is South Sudan unable to permanently end violence and conflict despite gaining independence from Sudan? Niyitunga and Wamaitha (2023) and Nyadera (2018: 71) find that the main contributing factors to the conflict in South Sudan are failure of governance, poverty, poor service delivery, unmet basic human needs and ethnicity. Rebellious groups either serve the interest of the political elites, parties, or interest groups (Raleigh, 2016: 286). Shulika and Okeke-Uzodike (2013) cement that ethnicity is the main source of conflict in South Sudan. The few

aforementioned scenarios simply demonstrate the rationale behind the displacement of people due to conflict. The following is an illustration showing the repercussions of violence that results in displacement in Mozambique.

AFRICA AGENDA 2063: "THE AFRICA WE WANT"

The Africa Agenda 2063 aspiration number 4, emphasizes the need to have a peaceful and secure Africa. Unfortunately, the status quo in Africa is characterized by conflicts and wars that lead to displacements of the poor and the proletariat. The Africa we want only exists in black and white; however, in reality, ordinary people continue to witness disgraceful and unsafe living environments due to conflicts and wars as previously discussed in this paper (IDMC, 2023). The picture depicted above simply shows the failure of the AU in championing and pioneering a peaceful and secure Africa. Until the AU takes a strong position against the ongoing conflicts and wars, the 'Africa we want' will remain a dream for many people.

METHODOLOGY

This is a theoretical paper which adopted the qualitative research method. Data to examine migration patterns and human security in Africa with reference to the African Agenda 2063 was compiled through a desktop study wherein newspapers, internet sources, scholarly journal articles, and government documents were used to support the stance of the paper. This paper utilized qualitative content analysis to help researchers understand and interpret written documents that are found in both the public and private domains.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The paper establishes a connection between socioeconomic progress and the geographical location of African emigration. Most African nations such as Algeria, Angola, etc. exhibit lower absolute and relative levels of migration beyond the continent. This supports the theory of migration transition, suggesting that impoverished inhabitants of African countries have limited ability to improve their living conditions. In addition, when these individuals have the opportunity to transform their lives, their movements are often confined within their African nations. The article also notes that the ongoing conflicts and violence in Africa result in a surge of people migrating to different countries in search of safety and peace.

This occurs under the guidance of the African Union (AU), which seems content with the current state of affairs in Africa. It is disheartening to realize that the goals outlined in Agenda 2063 are merely topics of discussion, while the majority of Africans continue to grapple with socioeconomic difficulties. Political instability and governments vulnerable to rebel forces are tragic and unfortunate realities. Consequently, poor governance leads to conflicts, which, in turn, leads to migration. This raises questions about the ability of the AU to enforce safety, peace, and security. In addition to dealing with natural disasters, there must be strategies in place to mitigate their effects, as they also lead to migration or displacement of people. This is corroborated by the

literature discussed in the paper. In summary, the paper explores various migration theories to explain why people migrate and finds that millions of people are affected by conflicts, wars, and natural disasters, leading to displacement. Moreover, migration within African countries causes some strain on governments because governments are expected to cater to and provide at least a refuge to migrants. Migration within African countries leads to the depopulation of rural areas because people migrate to urban areas for better opportunities. This is not without a set of challenges in urban areas because the influx of people to urban areas becomes a burden on urban governance due to the proliferation of slums, poverty, and crime (Selelo, Mokoeele, and Mnisi 2023).

The results show that economic possibilities are not the only variables driving migration in Africa; human security considerations like poverty, violence, conflict, and environmental degradation also play a role. Through the integration of these components into the African Agenda 2063, policymakers and academics can devise more comprehensive approaches that address the underlying causes of migration instead of just its manifestations. This concerted strategy may support the agenda's objective of advancing security and peace throughout the continent. To help shape policies that enable safe and lawful intra-African migration, which eventually promotes regional integration and economic cooperation, Agenda 2063 should acknowledge this trend. In addition, the results highlight the difficulties that migrants face, especially those who are unauthorized and frequently do not have legal protection. Policies that put human rights and safeguards for all migrants first can help advance the African Agenda 2063 by preserving migrants' safety and dignity and fostering social cohesion in host communities. The (MPFA) is failing to save the predicament of migration and human settlements. This is due to the persistence of socioeconomic ills experienced by people outside their home countries. The MPFA seeks to enable dignified, safe, and orderly migration. It promotes the adherence to international norms and rules in order to improve the socioeconomic well-being of migrants and the country (AU, 2018).

CONCLUSION

The paper concludes by highlighting that Africa is experiencing a surge in migration and a rise in anti-migrant sentiments, prompting policymakers to favour policies of deterrence over inclusivity. Therefore, the development and harmonization of migration management policies has become a crucial priority for African governments. Although these governments must address wars and conflicts, the United Arab Emirates also has a role to play in mitigating these situations. This is because the AU bears the responsibility of ensuring the realization of the aspirations outlined in Agenda 2063 across the continent. Furthermore, African countries need to start creating favourable working environments, building adequate infrastructure, revitalizing rural economies, attracting foreign direct investment (FDI) and addressing socioeconomic challenges to prevent people from migrating from their countries of origin. The effects of natural disasters must be mitigated through concerted efforts from both governments and the United Arab Emirates, and temporary measures and relief mechanisms must be implemented. The significance of this paper is to add to the existing body of knowledge by delving into and analysing migration patterns in Africa with specific reference to Africa Agenda 2063 aspiration 4. Understanding that the AU along with its member countries have acknowledged the importance of tackling these problems and have initiated measures to formulate policies and strategies to control migration and foster

growth. However, further actions are required to ensure the protection of the rights and respect of individuals who are forced to leave the country and to handle the difficulties of migration sustainably and fairly. The paper recommends that the AU should be at the forefront of addressing people who are on distress and stranded as a result of either forced migration or otherwise. It recommends that the MPFA of the AU should be strengthened and provided with more resources to assist migrants outside their native countries.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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